

Collaborators, Intermediaries and Gatekeepers: Doing Research Remotely in Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

For foreign researchers conducting research in rural Bangladesh, the establishment of relationships with local research collaborators, intermediaries and translators, who can facilitate their access to the communities, is essential. The closure of international borders and restrictions on travel to and within Bangladesh during the COVID-19 pandemic forced researchers to find new ways of reaching rural communities. In this paper, the author discusses her experience as a foreign researcher organising a face-to-face survey in a remote Bangladeshi village with the help of a Bangladeshi research assistant based in Australia and a community participant recruited and trained as surveyor. She discusses problems encountered during the conduct of the survey and argues that these problems are indicative of the different research paradigms adopted by the research team. Whereas the author approached the research within an interpretivist paradigm and was interested in understanding the participants' stories, the research assistant and the surveyor understood the research within a positivist paradigm and were focused on discovering the "truth". These problems illustrate the difficulty of doing research remotely with collaborators, intermediaries and translators who may have different understandings of what doing research encompasses and what is ethically appropriate.

KEYWORDS

Research paradigms; Research methods; Translation; Bangladesh.

INTRODUCTION

Even before the COVID-19 pandemic, conducting research in rural Bangladesh was a complex enterprise for foreign researchers (Stillman et al., 2022). Opportunities to travel to and within Bangladesh were limited, and the weather conditions and difficult terrain further limited access. It took whole day trips to travel to remote villages from the Bangladeshi capital, Dhaka, and flooding made the roads impassable for parts of the year. Foreigners were not allowed to stay overnight in the villages and their visits were closely supervised by village officials and their partners in local non-governmental organisations (NGOs). Local NGOs provided essential support without which projects could not have proceeded, but they were also gatekeepers who controlled access to the participants and to the data. The COVID-19 pandemic made it even harder for foreign researchers to conduct research in Bangladesh. The closure of international borders and restrictions to travel within Bangladesh, even for Bangladeshi researchers and NGO staff, forced those who wanted to continue their research to experiment with new ways of engaging remotely with participants and local collaborators. Ironically, switching to remote working enabled researchers who had local connections to avoid intermediaries and to interact directly with participants, at least with those who had access to mobile phones. However, for foreign researchers who are not fluent in Bangla, the need remained to work with intermediaries who speak the language. As this paper will report, this can impact the quality of the data collected.

In this paper, I discuss problems encountered during a survey which investigated how women in a remote Bangladeshi village who had taken part in an information technology for development (ICT4D) project preserved information that they had received during the project after the project ended. In December 2021, I organised a face-to-face survey of the 100 participants. The conduct of the survey required a familiarity with the ICT4D project and the village to locate the participants given that many of them had changed their phone numbers. I therefore decided to recruit one of the project participants who owned a smartphone and had experience working with NGOs to act as surveyor. In addition, I recruited a Bangladeshi researcher based in Australia who had previously done research in the village as a research assistant, translator and intermediary to facilitate the conduct of the research. In this paper, I relate how the survey was organised and the problems I encountered with working with intermediaries and their impact on the quality of the data collected.

BACKGROUND

Timely access to information is needed to perform many economic and social activities and to foster sustainable development. For marginalised communities who have limited access to information, preservation of previously accessed information can ensure that individuals will be able to access important information when they need it again. However, little is known about the ways marginalised communities in developing countries preserve information. My research is attempting to fill this gap by investigating how rural communities in developing countries access and preserve the information they need to support their agricultural activities and how their practices are impacted by cultural factors. It is positioned within an interpretivist paradigm and aims at collecting and analysing qualitative data. Whereas, positivist researchers believe that "there is a 'reality', or truth, to be discovered" and their research design usually consists of framing hypotheses, then testing them (Williamson, 2018,

p. 7), interpretivist researchers posit that there can be multiple realities, and that “none can be considered more ‘true’ than any other” (Williamson, 2018, p. 10). Their research design does not use hypotheses and does not aim at generalisability or replicability, but at recording the perspectives of participants as accurately as possible, and developing insights from the data by focusing on sensemaking, description and details (Battacharya, 2008). This is the approach that I took for the project discussed in this paper for which I used interviews and a survey. Surveys can be used in positivist and interpretivist research designs. Whereas positivist researchers develop and analyse surveys according to scientific principles, surveys with open-ended questions that can be analysed qualitatively can also be used in interpretivist research designs (Julien, 2008). Open-ended questions give the participants “opportunities for self-expression and elaboration” (Julien, 2008, p. 846) and therefore produce richer data. However, they can be challenging for respondents because they require more thinking and take more time to answer, and for the researchers because they are more difficult to interpret and analyse than answers to close questions (Julien, 2008). In this paper, I discuss the problems I encountered with using a qualitative survey with a mix of closed and open-ended questions.

SETTING UP AND CONDUCTING THE SURVEY

The aim of the research was to assess how the participants in an ICT4D project preserved the information they had accessed during the project after the project ended. Given that research conducted during the project had shown that some of the participants started writing information sent to them by text messages in notebooks after some of them lost data, I was particularly interested in finding out how widespread the practice of transcribing text messages in notebooks had been during the project and whether the participants still wrote information in notebooks two and a half years after the end of the project. Interviews conducted with a sample of eleven participants prior to the survey showed that all of them used a notebook during the project, that most of them (9 out of 11) transcribed at least some of the text messages sent to them in their notebooks, and that most of them still used those notebooks after the end of the project to check information (8 out of 11) and to write new information that they found useful (7 out of 11).

The survey included simple yes and no questions and multiple-choice questions, but also open-ended questions to give an opportunity to the participants to explain their practices. The participants were asked questions about their ownership and use of a phone after the end of the project and questions about their preferred methods to access and preserve information. Although I was interested in determining whether the practice of writing information in notebooks was common and what were the preferred methods to access and preserve information, I was more interested in hearing the women’s stories and their explanations for their preferences than in collecting quantitative data.

To facilitate the data collection, translation and analysis, the survey was conducted with the software Kobo Toolbox (<https://www.kobotoolbox.org/>), which can be used on a smartphone, allows for offline data collection and can accommodate Bangla script. The surveyor was trained to use the software by the research assistant via video calls. The research assistant helped her to set up the survey on her mobile phone, explained Kobo functionalities and the interview questions, and did a practice run of the survey with her. She explained to her the ethical guidelines regarding confidentiality of the data and instructed her on taking informed consent from the participants and on organising the payment of a small sum of money (BDT150 or about USD 2) to compensate them for their time. Throughout the course of the survey, she was in daily contact with her by phone and WhatsApp messaging to guide her and answer her questions. The surveyor was responsible for locating the 100 former project participants in her village (which spreads out over a large area and comprises several hamlets). She managed to locate all the participants and to interview 98 of them (95 in person and 3 by phone). Two women who had left the village were unable to take part in the survey because they did not have easy access to a phone. The research assistant translated the survey responses and conducted an interview with the surveyor after the end of the survey, which she also translated. I downloaded the quantitative reports produced by KoboToolbox, which gave me a preliminary understanding of the findings, then analysed the survey answers after they were translated.

The data collected during the survey shows that the majority of the women (91 out of 98) used notebooks during the project and that two and a half years after the end of the project most of those women (77 out of 91) still used their notebooks to check information they had written in them because that information was still useful for them. By then, most of the project phones were no longer working. Most of the women no longer had access to a smartphone or to the internet and had to rely on other sources of information. In those circumstances, the localised information developed during the ICT4D project which the women had preserved in their notebooks represented an important source of information for them. The survey findings are analysed in more details in another paper (Frings-Hessami, 2022). In the remainder of this paper, I will discuss the problems encountered during the data collection.

PROBLEMS ENCOUNTERED

The first findings to which I had access after the completion of the survey were the quantitative reports generated by Kobo Toolbox. These reports raised questions about the quality of the data because the answers to two of the

questions differed markedly from the findings of the interviews which had been conducted before the survey. I then asked the research assistant to organise an interview with the surveyor to ask her questions about her experience with conducting the survey in general, and in particular about the way she asked the two questions which had received discordant answers and about her opinion on those discordances based on her knowledge of the project and of the participants. This interview could not be organised until six weeks later because the surveyor was not available. The research assistant provided me three days after the interview with a verbal summary of the interview, but it took another six weeks for her to complete its translation because she had other commitments. The surveyor's answers to those questions and the way the research assistant relayed those answers to me provide some interesting insights into some of the problems associated with doing research remotely via intermediaries.

The first question for which the answers were markedly different from those given by a sample of participants interviewed before the survey is the question which asked the women if they transcribed SMS in their notebooks during the ICT4D project and, if they did it, whether they wrote all of the SMS sent to them or only those they found useful. The survey recorded only one woman as having answered that she wrote all the SMS and six as saying that they wrote the SMS they found useful. These numbers looked strange because they were fewer than the nine interviewees out of eleven who said that they wrote at least some of the SMS in their notebooks. When matched with the interviews, the data showed that of those nine women, seven were marked in the survey as having answered "no" to the question asking them if they transcribed SMS in their notebooks.

During her interview with the research assistant, the surveyor explained that when the women answered "yes" to that question, she checked their notebooks. If she saw SMS in their notebooks, she marked their answers as "yes"; if she did not, she marked them as "no". This is problematic for two reasons: firstly, because looking through the women's notebooks was an unnecessary invasion of their privacy, and secondly, because the surveyor did not accurately record what the participants told her. This did not result from an intentional falsification of the data on her part, but from her inexperience and her misunderstanding of the purpose of the research and of the instructions given to her by the research assistant who checked daily the data that she entered in Kobo Toolbox. After the research assistant reviewed the data collected on the first day of the survey, she had discussed with the surveyor some concerns that she had about the quality of the data because some of the free text answers were very short. She had advised her to ask for more details and to record those details in the survey. She had also advised her to "cross-check" data by asking further questions when the answers to two questions appeared to contradict each other. The surveyor understood this as suggesting that she checked the women's notebooks for evidence to confirm their answers. An analysis of the data shows that for the first three participants whom she interviewed on the first day of the data collection, she recorded "yes" to the SMS question, but that subsequently she only recorded four more yeses to that question. For those four participants, she took a picture of their notebooks showing text messages as evidence that they wrote SMS in their notebooks. If she could not find SMS in their notebooks or if the participants did not show her their notebooks, she marked their answers as "no". Since she only took pictures of 39 notebooks, a large number of the women who said that they had kept a notebook during the project may have been marked as answering "no" simply because they did not show her their notebooks. Moreover, among the women who showed her a notebook, some of them may have had more than one notebook and did not show the notebook that included SMS. It is also possible that she browsed the notebooks quickly and did not see the SMS that may have been written in them. In any case, not recording as "yes" the answers of women who did not show evidence of having written SMS in their notebooks did not produce an accurate report of the stories that the women told her, which is what the research was interested in capturing. When the research assistant asked her whether she thought that it was "correct" that only a few women wrote the SMS in their notebooks and whether she remembered if many women were doing it during the ICT4D project, her answer was defensive: "I am confident that I have done it right!", focusing on her conduct of the survey rather than on her recollections of previous practices, and the research assistant did not follow up with more questions about her recollections. The research assistant did not report this problem to me when, three days later, she summarised her interview with the surveyor. When I asked her about it after I read her translation of the interview six weeks later, she said that she did not know that the surveyor was checking the notebooks until the end of the survey and that when she heard about data being changed, she did not think that it was a problem because it had happened in "only a few cases".

The second question that produced discordant answers is the question which asked women if they were still writing information in notebooks. For this question, all the women were marked as having answered "no". This was strange because during the interviews conducted before the survey, seven women talked about continuing to write information in their notebooks. Like for the previous question, this can be attributed to the fact that the surveyor recorded the participants' answers as "no" if she could not see evidence of the women writing in their notebooks. When the research assistant asked her if she thought that it was "correct" that none of the women were still writing in their notebooks, she understood the question as being about the process she followed rather than about her factual knowledge and answered that she was confident that what she recorded was correct because she checked the notebooks. However, some women may have showed her an older notebook (e.g. their project notebook) rather than

their most recent one or the information recorded in their notebooks may not have been dated so that she did not recognise it as recent information. Like for the first question, the research assistant did not report to me that some answers had been changed, only telling me that the surveyor thought that it was “correct” to say that the women no longer wrote in their notebooks.

It appears that there was a misunderstanding both from the part of the surveyor and from the part of the research assistant about the objectives of the research. Although both of them had been briefed about the objectives and the methodology, both appear to have been focused on discovering the “truth”, backed by evidence, about the participants writing practices, rather than on accurately recording the women’s stories. They were working within a positivist paradigm whereas my research was positioned within an interpretivist paradigm. I was more interested in hearing why the women used notebooks and how they used them than in knowing how many of them used them. Arguably, this was difficult to achieve through a survey, and expecting an inexperienced surveyor to conduct the survey may have been too ambitious. Because of the changes made to the data and because it was not clear how many entries were affected, I had to discard the answers to the two questions where data had been changed. This was very disappointing because those two questions were at the centre of my research. The survey, nevertheless, provided interesting data and useful lessons for the next stages of my research. However, because I did not hear of the problems that had occurred in the survey until four months after they happened, I was not able to take them into account when I designed a survey for another village. (Fortunately, the same problems did not occur with that survey). The frustration of not having been able to gather reliable data was compounded by the frustration of only hearing about the problems several months later. The research assistant had become a gatekeeper who did not report the problems because she did not see what took place as inappropriate. Her focus on finding the “truth” about the number of women who wrote in notebooks made her neglect the importance of maintaining the integrity of the data.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The problems encountered with this survey illustrate some of the difficulties associated with doing research in Bangladesh: the problem of reaching participants, the need to rely on intermediaries and translators, and the pitfalls of cross-cultural communication. As the COVID-19 pandemic forced researchers to conduct research remotely, I attempted to minimise the number of intermediaries by working with a research assistant who could reach the participants and the surveyor directly, by phone, thereby avoiding having to rely on local NGO workers as intermediaries. However, in the course of conducting the survey, different understandings of the purpose of the research and of the role of the researchers surfaced, which affected the quality of the data collected.

Efforts had been made to include the surveyor as a co-researcher. She was selected because she was a participant in the target group and knew the community well. The interview questions were discussed with her and her feedback helped refining them. She played an essential role in recruiting the participants and her participation undoubtedly encouraged others to take part in the survey. She contributed her insider perspective throughout the course of the survey through her daily discussions with the research assistant, thereby giving a voice to her community (Boylorn, 2008). However, due to her inexperience, setting up the survey took longer than expected as she had to be trained remotely in conducting research and using the app, and she took initiatives that were at odds with the research design. In addition, her involvement as a participant-cum-co-researcher may have impacted the data collected in other ways. Her personal preferences may have influenced the way she explained the questions and she may have influenced the participants in responding in a particular way by suggesting some answers and this may have impacted on the quality of the data collected.

The research assistant had been selected for her knowledge of the village where the survey was conducted. She collaborated as a co-researcher in the elaboration of the questionnaire, she recruited and trained the surveyor and was in daily contact with her during the conduct of the survey, then she translated the survey data. Her contributions were essential to the conduct of the research, but her knowledge of the language placed her in the position of an intermediary between me and the surveyor and the fine line between being an intermediary and becoming a gatekeeper was crossed when she did not promptly report problems that were taking place. She did not intentionally hide the problems, but because of her different understanding of the research objectives, she became a gatekeeper who restricted my access to important information. The most serious miscommunication relates to the two cases of data modification that she did not report to me, instead reporting that the surveyor thought that the data she collected correctly reflected what had happen or was happening in the community. Her use of the word “correct” in the questions she asked to the surveyor when trying to understand the discordances between the survey data and the findings from interviews conducted before the survey reflects the positivist paradigm through which she saw and presented the research. She was focused on finding the “truth” about the use of notebooks by participants whereas I was interested in accurately capturing their stories and trying to understand and make sense of them. We were seeing the research through different paradigms and these two paradigms clashed during the conduct of the research, affecting the quality of the data, but at the same time providing useful insights into the different understandings of research that research collaborators may have and how they may affect the conduct of their research.

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